

PIEZORESISTANCE CHARACTERIZATION OF PVDF-MWNT NANOCOMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

Multifunctional materials possess multiple desirable attributes concurrently such as improved thermal, mechanical, electrical, chemical properties etc. Several research studies have highlighted the benefits of utilizing nanoparticles, including carbon nanotubes (CNT), dispersed in a polymer matrix to fabricate multifunctional materials [1-3]. Such nanocomposites can possess improved mechanical, electrical and/or thermal properties, and have numerous applications as sensors [4-6], electrodes [7,8], actuators [9-11], structural materials [12,13], adhesives [14,15] etc.

Piezoresistance is a passive phenomenon that can be used for sensing of load/pressure through variations in a material's electrical resistance. The mechanisms of piezoresistance can vary between materials and through various design configurations these materials can be used for pressure and strain sensing [16]. One mechanism is found in conventional metallic strain gages commonly used in structural strain monitoring. These sensors rely on resistance change because of a changing geometry (definable by their Poisson's ration) due to external strain [16]. Metallic strain gages possess appreciable linearity and sensitivity, measurable by gage factors (change in resistance: change in strain) as high as 2, however, they are limited to measuring strains less than 2%. Another piezoresistance mechanism is found in semiconductor-based pressure sensors where deformation of a doped semiconductor lattice will result in a change of the charge carrier's mobility and the material's resistance. The gage factors for these devices are around 200 (recently shown to be as high as 843 [17]). However semiconductor-based pressure sensors are also limited to small strain ranges, which are around 0.5%.

A third piezoresistance mechanism, which is the focus of this study, is found in composites containing conductive fillers. These composites consist of a soft material (e.g. polymers, rubbers) filled with a conductive filler. The inter-particle distances of the filler must be small enough ($< 2\text{nm}$ [18]) so as to allow for formation of conductive paths across one measurement surface to the other. These conductive paths form when the concentration of fillers reaches a critical threshold value described by percolation theory [19,20]. Deformation of the conductor filled composite will change the mean particle distance and therefore change the material's resistivity. Such materials possess appreciable sensitivities with gage factors in the range of 2-10. Although conductive polymer composites suffer from the disadvantages of non-linearity, hysteresis and temperature drifts, they are operational over large strains ($\pm 100\%$ for elastomers) and are simple and cost-effective to manufacture [16]. These advantages make them potential sensing elements for applications requiring compliant materials such as electronic-textiles, artificial skins and other large deformation measurements [21].

Several recent studies have investigated the piezoresistance of conductive nanoparticle composites. Bautista-Quijano et al.[22] examined the piezoresistance of composites of polysulfone and MWNT, fabricated using solvent casting. The composites, containing only 0.5 wt% MWNT, were applied as strain gages for failure testing of Aluminum and evaluated against conventional metallic strain gages. Loh et al.[23] fabricated thin-film strain sensors by dispersing single-wall carbon nanotubes (SWNT) into poly(sodium 4-styrene-sulfonate) and poly(vinyl-alcohol) by layer-by-layer processing. The non-linearity, decay and hysteresis observed in the piezoresistance were predicted using an equivalent RC-circuit model. Hu et al.[18] have

modeled the piezoresistance of epoxy-MWNT composites using Monte-Carlo simulations of 3D resistor networks. Investigations by Knite et al.[24] and by Wichmann et al.[25] have compared the strain sensing capability between carbon black and MWNT in poly(isoprene) composites. Studies by Chen et al.[26] and Stubler et al.[27] have examined hysteresis issues in piezoresistance of conductive composites.

Lu et al. [28] have found the gage factor of PDMS-MWNT composites to be as high as 12. They also demonstrated the applicability of these composites to MEMS through lithography assisted fabrication of micro-pressure sensors. Hwang et al. [29] have investigated the effect of surface modification of MWNT for better dispersion in PDMS and found improvements in piezoresistance sensitivity. Dang et al. [30] have fabricated piezoresistive PDMS-MWNT composites using high and low aspect ratio MWNT.

The objective of this study is to investigate the effect of MWNT concentration on the electrical properties and piezoresistance of Polyvinylidene Fluoride-MWNT (PVDF-MWNT) composites prepared by high shear melt mixing. PVDF is a thermoplastic polymer with good thermal stability, allowing for ease of processing, and flexibility. The electrical and rheological properties are studied in the context of filler percolation networks and piezoresistive properties of the composites are investigated, modeled and correlated with their observed morphology.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Polyvinylidene Fluoride (PVDF) was used as the matrix phase (Kynar 740, Arkema S.A.) in pellet form. The PVDF has a density of 1.78 g/cm^3 . Thin Multiwall Carbon Nanotubes (MWNT) were used as the nanoparticle filler phase in this study (NC7000, Nanocyl). The MWNT had a reported diameter of 10 nm, average length of $1.5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and a carbon purity of 90%.

2.2 Nanocomposite Preparation

Nanocomposites between PVDF and MWNT were prepared by a high shear mixing process on a 15 ml twin screw microcompounder. The MWNT powder (in concentrations between 0-10

wt%) and PVDF pellets were added to the microcompounder simultaneously. The high shear mixing process was performed at a temperature of $220 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and mixing speed of 200 rpm for 10 minutes. The extruded material was then cut into pellets and compression molded into a disc shape geometry (12.5 mm dia, 1.6 mm thick) at a pressure of 1.3 MPa and a temperature of $220 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for a melt time of 5 min and press time of 5 min.

2.3 Characterization Methods

Morphology of the freeze-fractured composite cross-sections was observed using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) operated under secondary electron mode at 20 kV. The electrical conductivity and permittivity of the PVDF-MWNT nanocomposites was obtained in a dielectric impedance analyzer (Alpha-N Analyzer, Novocontrol Technologies) operated at 1 Vrms scanning between a frequency of 10^{-1} Hz to 10^5 Hz . and The piezoresistance behavior of the TPU-MWNT nanocomposites was captured using a custom-made force-resistance measurement setup (Figure 1). The setup consisted of a high precision source meter (model 2400, Keithley Instruments Inc) in a two-wire resistance measurement configuration coupled with a micromechanical-testing system (model 5848, Instron) reading resistance and stress-strain information to a National Instrument's LabView data acquisition system. Starting from a pre-load of 50 N, the disc samples for piezoresistance characterization were compressed between two copper electrodes (insulated on the opposite side) in a quasi-static condition at a rate of 1 mm/min (0.003 s^{-1}) until a final force of 30 kN was reached. Three or more samples were used for all electrical and piezoresistance testing and averaged, and prior to testing the samples were cleaned with ethanol, dried and platinum sputter-coated to ensure adequate electrical contact.

Figure 1. Custom-made setup for piezoresistance measurement.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 2. Morphologies of (a) neat PVDF, (b) 0.25 wt%, (c) 1.5 wt%, and (d) 6 wt% MWNT containing PVDF nanocomposites.

3.1 Morphology of PVDF-MWNT Nanocomposites

The morphology of the nanocomposites was characterized using SEM. Figure 2 shows the freeze-fractured cross-section morphologies of PVDF and its nanocomposites containing 0.25, 1.5 and 6 wt% MWNT. The MWNT are apparent upon comparison of the neat PVDF morphology with that of its nanocomposites. At 0.25 wt% MWNT (Figure 2b) content, the MWNT are dispersed uniformly but are sparse and separated from each other on the order of several hundred nanometers. Further addition of MWNT to 1.5 wt% (Figure 2c) reveals a denser distribution of MWNT with shorter inter-particle distances. A consequence of further MWNT addition is the appearance of aggregate particles with their locations being regions highlighted by greater intensity in the e-beam signal. At high MWNT concentrations, e.g. 6 wt% MWNT (Figure 2d), there is complete interconnectivity between MWNT particles. A greater degree of aggregation of MWNT particles is also present.

3.2 Electrical Properties of PVDF-MWNT Nanocomposites

Dielectric impedance spectroscopy (DIS) was used to characterize the electrical conductivity as well as the dielectric permittivity of the PVDF-MWNT nanocomposites filled with various content of MWNT filler. Impedance spectroscopy is used to measure the impedance of the composite at various frequencies and then estimate the conductivity and permittivity of the material through fitting the data to an Resistance-Capacitance circuit in parallel[31]. Figure 3a, shows the real electrical conductivity data for PE-MWNT nanocomposites. The electrical conductivity of neat PVDF is dependent on the applied frequency which at 0.1 Hz is 10^{-13} S/cm, indicative of an insulating behavior. By incorporating 0.25 and 0.5 wt% MWNT filler content, the electrical conductivity increases slightly but is still insulating. At 1.0 wt% MWNT filler content, the electrical conductivity is 10^{-9} S/cm, independent of frequency and is electronically conducting indicating the establishment of interparticle contacts and networking of MWNT particles within the matrix. At 10 wt% MWNT, a maximum conductivity of 10^{-2} S/cm is achieved which is well within the minimum conductivity of 10^{-5} S/cm required for

electrostatic discharge (ESD) material applications [32,33].

The permittivity (Figure 3b) of neat PVDF at 0.1 Hz is 15.0. Addition of 0.25 wt% MWNT increases the permittivity to 17.1, which indicates a greater ability to store charge (capacitance). Increased permittivity in filled materials is observed because of a greater number of interfaces (surface area) near the electrode regions allowing for larger amounts of charges to be stored. This effect is most prominent at low frequencies as it allows more time for charges to migrate. The maximum permittivity of 39.4 occurs at 1.0 wt% MWNT content, beyond which a filler particle network has formed throughout and the material loses its dielectric characteristic.

Figure 3. Electrical conductivity (a) and dielectric permittivity (b) of PVDF and PVDF-MWNT nanocomposites

3.3 Percolation Behavior in PVDF-MWNT Nanocomposites

The electrical and rheological behaviors indicate the existence of a percolation threshold concentration of MWNT, beyond which the electrical conductivity and viscosity exhibit a sharp rise (transition) in value. The percolation point describes a concentration where interconnectivity between randomly placed particles in a confined space results in continuous paths across the space. The percolation threshold can be inferred from changes in certain nanocomposite properties, such as electrical and rheological properties, where filler particles (e.g. MWNT) exert significant influence. The sharp transition in properties during statistical (random) percolation can be modeled using the following power-law form, of the properties under consideration:

$$\sigma = A(\phi - \phi_c)^t \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$\eta = A(\phi - \phi_c)^t \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where σ is the conductivity, η is the viscosity, ϕ is the filler volume fraction, ϕ_c is the filler volume fraction at percolation. The exponential terms, t , and pre-exponential A , are fitting parameters which under certain fit constraints describe the dimensionality of the filler particle network.

The electrical conductivity and viscosity of PVDF nanocomposite is plotted in Figure 4 with respect to volume fraction. The percolation threshold transition behavior is apparent in Figure 4. Percolation thresholds (ϕ_c) were determined by fitting Eq. 1 and 2 to the data plotted in Figure 4, using a least-squares optimization routine in MATLAB and the results are summarized in Table 1. The electrical percolation threshold was found to be 1.17 vol% (1.31 wt%) with an R^2 of 0.999, while the rheological percolation threshold was found to be 1.70 vol% (1.91 wt%) with an R^2 of 0.977.

Table 1. Power-law fitting parameters for PVDF nanocomposites

	A	ϕ_c	t	R^2
σ	2.32 S/cm	1.31 wt%	1.72	0.999
η	1.33×10^7 Pa-s	1.91 wt%	1.14	0.977

The results indicate that the apparent rheological percolation point exists at higher MWNT content than the electrical percolation point. This is contradictory of the general observation in polymer nanocomposites where the rheological

percolation point exists at lower MWNT content than the electrical point. This is because electrical contact requires MWNT particles to be sufficiently close together, which is possible when they are either (1) in direct contact with each other (ohmic conduction) or (2) are close enough for electron tunneling to occur (non-ohmic). Rheological percolation does not require such short inter-particle distances, and hence high MWNT content. Rheological percolation is based on preventing polymer chains from relaxing after an applied deformation. As polymer chains constitute the particle-to-particle boundary, the distance between adjacent particles does not have to be as small as electrical conduction for rheological percolation effects to be apparent.

The higher apparent rheological percolation point in PVDF-nanocomposites is believed to be because of the gradual increase in viscosity, as opposed to a sharp increase, when MWNT content is increased. This gradual increase is caused by neat PVDF having a high viscosity to begin with. The viscosity of neat PVDF is 2.5×10^4 Pa-s, which is higher when compared to other thermoplastic polymers. With the matrix viscosity already very high (due to the physical chemistry of PVDF), the room for improvement in viscosity with MWNT addition is severely restricted. In an effort to reduce PVDF viscosity, the test temperature was raised to 300 °C, however the viscosity still remained high at 1.2×10^4 Pa-s while the risk of polymer deterioration increased.

Figure 4. Percolation threshold transition in electrical conductivity (square) and viscosity (circle).

3.3 Piezoresistance of PVDF-MWNT Nanocomposites

The compressive piezoresistance of the MWNT filled PVDF nanocomposites was measured in quasi-static conditions at a strain rate of 1 mm/min ($\sim 0.01\text{s}^{-1}$). Figure 5a plots the stress-strain and resistance strain behavior of the MWNT nanocomposites. The curves in Figure 5a are composite averages of 3 or more samples. The resistance and stress signal in Figure 5a can be parameterized and plotted against one another as shown in Figure 5b. The resistance-stress behavior of these nanocomposites can be subdivided into three basic regions. The first/initial region is where full contact is established between the compressing platens and the sample. Most of the resistance change is observed in this region, regardless of filler content. This initial resistance change originates from establishing a well-defined electrical contact between the compression platen and the sample surface during the initial stages of deformation; which in turn depends on establishing a well-defined mechanical contact without any slack. It can be observed from the strain-stress plots (Figure 5a), that the 'toe'-region terminates in the first 10 MPa of applied pressure indicating all of the slack has been overcome.

The second region of compressive deformation is where elastic compression takes place. This region occurs at stresses greater than 10 MPa and is characterized by a linear strain-stress behavior. The resistance signal in this region continues to decrease, however, not as fast as the initial contact region. The third deformation region observed during the compression process is the plastic deformation zone. This occurs where the strain-stress curve begins to yield (softening).

The aforementioned observations suggest that the resistance-stress dependence in PVDF-nanocomposites is non-linear, non-monotonous and complex. It does however, correlate well with the different stages of deformation observed on the strain-stress curve. In order to compare the response of PVDF nanocomposites of different filler content and hence different conductivities, a relative resistance response must be considered, where the resistance is plotted as a ratio in reference to the initial resistance at the point of first contact. In addition, comparisons of relative resistance change between different nanocomposite compositions can be made by plotting iso-stress lines as shown in Figure 5c.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3. Piezoresistance of PVDF-MWNT nanocomposites.

A general observation from Figure 5c is that compositions closer to the percolation point (2, 3 and 4 wt%) display greater sensitivity in the resistance signal, than those compositions further away (6, 8 and 10 wt%), neglecting the change due to contact effects (< 10 MPa). This greater

sensitivity is observed in both elastic and plastic portions of deformation. In the elastic portion (~ 10-100 MPa) the resistance signal at low compositions displays a greater decrease corresponding to further MWNT inter-particle distance reduction and network enhancement due to a uniaxial but largely affine deformation. In the plastic portion (>150 MPa) the resistance signal at low compositions undergoes a sharp rise, even above its initial zero-stress value. This sharp rise is associated with MWNT network destruction due to the plastic flow induced by shear-stresses that develop at high strain levels.

4. Conclusions

In this study, nanocomposites of PVDF and MWNT were fabricated by twin-screw blending and compression molding. The morphology of the blends was characterized as individual and dispersed MWNT at low filler contents (0.25 wt%), whereas it was networked but also aggregated at high filler contents (6 wt%). The networking of MWNTs was also clearly depicted in the electrical conductivity of the nanocomposites, which underwent a sharp rise between 0.5 and 1.5 wt% MWNT. The statistical percolation threshold for PVDF-MWNT nanocomposites was found to be 0.95 wt% (0.85 vol.%). At 0.1 Hz, the maximum conductivity achieved in the nanocomposites was 10^{-2} S/cm (10 wt%), while the maximum dielectric permittivity was 39.4 (1.0 wt%). Piezoresistance investigation of the PVDF-MWNT nanocomposites revealed a three stage deformation (contact, elastic and plastic deformation) process which has a direct influence on the MWNT networks in the nanocomposites and hence on the material's electrical resistivity. The resistance was observed to decrease during elastic deformation, while increase during plastic deformation, corresponding to reducing and increasing inter-particle distances between the MWNT, respectively.

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